

SHIFT 02-373 - FUNGAL INTERACTIONS WITH ARCHITECTONIC MATERIALS: ELECTRON MICROSCOPY INSIGHTS (ID 1364)

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Poster Rating

Abstract

Abstract Body

Our interdisciplinary research pioneers the integration of microorganisms into architectural materials, yielding groundbreaking living skin with unprecedented properties. This innovative approach aligns with the paradigm shift in Engineered Living Materials (ELMs), emphasizing biointeractions and sustainability. Moreover, it underscores the importance of understanding intricate biointeractions between biological surfaces and architectural materials, addressing the urgent need for sustainable architecture.

Identifying and quantifying the parameters governing the interaction between solid architectural materials and biological surfaces, such as fungal cell walls, is imperative. While many studies focus on using mycelium to produce various building blocks like bricks or panels, a knowledge gap exists regarding the biointerface interaction between living cells and architectural materials. Optimizing the model of these interactions and proposing robust investigation methods is crucial.

This study aimed to optimize procedures for electron microscopy observations of microorganisms interacting with various solid materials. *Aureobasidium pullulans* was exposed to various materials (eg. wood, concrete, polymers, nanoparticles) and prepared for observations. Briefly, samples underwent washing, fixation in 3% buffered glutaraldehyde, osmium tetroxide contrasting, dehydration in ethanol solutions, resin rinsing, ultramicrotome sectioning, and observation in a Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM).

The study revealed intricate interactions between the investigated fungus and the applied materials. We established a protocol for preparing biological samples for TEM observations of the interface between cells and various solid architectural materials.

Such knowledge can be utilized for further investigations of microorganism-based effective systems, not only for creating new building blocks for architecture but also for developing and assessing novel functionalities.

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